

CREATIVE COMMONS LICENCE: THE PANACEA FOR EXCESSIVE AND RIGID COPYRIGHT PROTECTION

George R.C. Ibekwe^{1*}, Thomas O. Okaba²

^{1*}Deputy Director Academics, Nigerian Law School.

²D.L., LL. B. (Abuja) B. L, LL. M. (Keffi) Nigerian Law School, Lagos, Campus.

* **Correspondence:** George R.C. Ibekwe

*The authors declare
that no funding was
received for this work.*

Received: 01-April-2026

Accepted: 17-May-2026

Published: 25-May-2026

Copyright © 2026, Authors retain copyright. Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> (CC BY 4.0 deed)

This article is published by **MSI Publishers** in **MSI Journal of Arts, Law and Justice (MSIJALJ)**
ISSN 3049-0839 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers

Volume: 3, Issue: 5 (May-2026)

ABSTRACT: Copyright law evolved to provide incentives to owners of creative works by granting them limited monopoly over their works and protecting same for a period of time. However, the introduction of copyright over creative works and its subsequent excessive and rigid regime has caused restrictive access to knowledge and information and has consequently led to ownership and commercialization of knowledge. This has not only limited the right to freedom of expression and access to knowledge, but has also inhibited innovation and development globally. This circumstance gave birth to Creative Commons which came with the goal of helping the knowledge-seeking global citizens to have access to copyrighted works with little or no restrictions using Creative Commons Licence as a legal tool. This work employed the doctrinal methodology and ex-rayed Creative Commons Licence as a Panacea for Excessive and Rigid Copyright protection. It found that copyright protection turned out excessive and rigid thereby inhibits creativity, access to knowledge and information, educational and research materials. It recommended inter alia that copyright owners should embrace and utilise the Creative Commons Licence window to allow people have access to their works

with little or no restrictions and that amendments to Copyright enactments aimed at demystifying the strong and rigid copyright protection be made.

Keywords: *Creative Commons, Creative Commons Licences, Copyright, Excessive, Rigid protection.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This article demonstrates how copyright evolved and how it progressively became excessive and rigid and thereby inhibiting creativity and access to knowledge and information. References are made to the United Kingdom and United States jurisdictions to show how increasingly copyright became excessive. It examined Creative Commons (CC), CC goal and mission and Creative Commons in Nigeria. The article further examined Creative Commons Licence as a mechanism to overcome the excessive protection conferred on authors by copyright. It also discussed the relationship between CC Licence and Copyright, stating that CC licence can be deployed as a voluntary tool for the reduction of copyrights of authors of creative works for the purpose of open knowledge, knowledge and information circulation; and the enhancement of creativity, innovation and development, among others. It also made robust recommendations to all stakeholders involved.

2.0 COPYRIGHT AND ITS PROGRESSIVELY EXCESSIVE AND RIGID PROTECTION

Copyright is one of the legal branches of intellectual property law that secures immaterial objects. It is one of the three branches of intellectual property which give the owner exclusive right to authorise or prohibit certain uses of his work by others. Copyright is the exclusive right conferred by law on the creator or author of copyright-eligible works. Copyright is a protection that enables the creator or author to recover from the mental and material resources invested in the creation of his work.

The motivations underlying copyright law today are quite different from those which led to its original creation in England several centuries ago. Until the advent of the printing press, nobody needed protection against others who might steal their work. The process of copying books was so tedious that few copies of most books were

ever made. However, during the mid sixteenth century the invention of the printing press technology allowed large-scale production of written works for the first time as well as reduced their reproduction costs, which at the same time raised publishers and book vendors' profits and induced piracy. This revolution in a way affected how information was spread, which was seen as a threat by the monarchy that believed that it could motivate political and religious rebellion. As a response to this concern, in 1534, the government determined that any work should be approved by the official censor before being published and in 1557 the stationers' company was established and made responsible for granting the said approval. At the same time, members of the stationer's company had the exclusive and perpetual right to published approved works. Of course, the stationer' monopoly came with a catch, a censorship system which gave the king the ability to control what was printed. At this stage copyright protection did not aim at protecting any right of the respective authors rather, it was a legal censor tool in reaction to the challenge posed by the new technologies for the reproduction and distribution of human expression. Subsequently, this was followed by the enactment of the Statute of Anne, the Copyright Act of 1710 which brought some changes to the concept of copyright. The Statute of Anne had a title 'An Act for the encouragement of learning, by vesting the copies of printed books in the authors or purchasers of such copies during the times therein mentioned.' The Act conferred the sole right and liberty of printing books on authors and their assigns, and enforcement was depended on registering the book's title before publication with the stationers' company. The right however lasted for 14 years from first publication but if the author was still living at the end, the right was "returned" to him for another 14years.

As expounded above, in the 15/16th centuries, Copyright was seen as reaction to the challenge posed by the new printing technologies and later as incentives to owners of creative works by granting them limited monopoly over their works for short period of time

However, rights conferred by copyright and its tenure became expanded and elongated by parliaments and therefore became stronger than anticipated to the detriment of public access to knowledge and information. In the case *Eldred v*

Ashcroft, the cause of action was that US Congress passed extending copyright terms by 20 years for both existing and new copyright works, taking it from 50 to 70 years.

The protection offered by the 1790 Copyright Act of the US was limited for authors of works that had been printed within the United States, being a citizen or residence. Therefore, no protection was extended to foreign authors as it exists presently. Also, at the initial stage of copyright there were requirements to be met before protection such as Publication of the work, deposition and/or filing of copies of works at the appropriate office which requirements have ceased to exist as protection is now automatic upon creation of work.

By the Berne Convention of 1886 and the Berlin Revision of the Convention in 1908 a multi-national expansive system of copyright protection evolved under which either the personal connection of the author with a member state or first publication in a member state was to secure copyright in the other under the principle of national treatment. Also, by the convention, protection now arises out of the act of creation itself without any condition of registration or other formality (a situation which obliged Britain to abandon even the traditional requirement of stationers' company registration before suing) and the period of protection for most types of copyright work was lifted to at least the author's life and fifty years.

Under the current copyright regime in Nigeria, copyright term in literary, musical and artistic works, excluding photographs, is for the lifetime of the author and seventy (70) years thereafter the death of the author. Where the author is a body corporate, or the work is made by or under the direction or control of the government, a state authority or a prescribed international body, the term is seventy years, calculated from the year immediately following that in which the work was first published. While copyright in cinematography films and photographs, sound recording and Broadcasts all have fifty (50) years term each.

Again, copyright, which historically provided protection for books and written articles only, has now been extended to variety of creative works. For instance, under the Nigerian regime, works eligible for copyright are – (a) Literary works, (c) Musical works, (c) Artistic works, (d) Cinematography works, (e) Sound recording and (f) Broadcasts. Also, copyright which ab initio simply protects unauthorized

copying, and reproduction has been so expanded to now prohibit adaptation, translation, performance, and communication for literary, artistic and musical works.

The excessive and rigid regime of copyright protection has encumbered the free flow of information, knowledge and freedom of expression. It has consequently hindered creativity and transformative use and reuse of intellectual creations. This is because copyright has made the use, reuse, distribution and improvement on creative works highly restrictive and commercialized by providing authors with negative cum numerous exclusive rights and longer terms than necessary. Commenting on the nature of copyright under the English Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988 (similar to section 6(1) of the Nigerian Act), the English Court of Appeal in *Ashdown v Telegraph Group Ltd.* noted that:

Copyright is essentially not positive but a negative right. No provision of the 1988 Act confers in terms, upon the owner of copyright in a literary work, the right to publish it. The Act gives the owner of the copyright the right to prevent others from doing that which the Act recognises the owner alone has a right to do. Thus, copyright is antithetical to freedom of expression. It prevents all, save the owner of the copyright, from expressing information in the form of the literary work protected by the copyright.

To sustain creativity and development, existing creative works must be used and regenerated as there is seldom any creation that is entirely new. As stated by Justice Story, in literature, in science and in art, there and can be few, if any, things, which in abstract sense are strictly new and original throughout. Every book in literature, science and art borrows and must necessarily borrow and use much which was well known and used before.'

Copyright is capable of compelling a user of an existing work to abandon the reuse of such work or not to use same in the manner and sense the new author would have used it and when an author forgoes the opportunity to reuse the work of another author or its portion out of fear that the use might be challenged as infringement of copyright, there would be huge loss of knowledge not only to that author but also to the public. The public cannot benefit from insights that the second author's reuse of the first author's work would have enabled.

Although copyright through the enabling legal framework had developed certain exceptions and defences to copyright in addition to the tenuring of copyright to certain number of years, all of these have proved to be inadequate in the fast-growing world which requires fast and widespread information, knowledge, creativity and development.

Due to this rigid copyright protection, individuals and organizations began to mount agitation and campaigns for open access to information and knowledge; calling for waiver or diminution of copyrights in creative works. It is in view of the foregoing that Creative Commons emerged with the aim to balance the copyrights of authors with the need to allow open and widespread use, re-use, distribution and remix of copyrighted creative works. Creative Commons does this by arranging a special licence (cc licence) which enables copyrights owners/holders to diminish their rights to the extent as to be contained in the licence.

2.0 CREATIVE COMMONS

The background facts leading to the formation of creative commons are that in 1998 the US Congress passed into law the Copyright Extension Act which extended copyright terms by 20 years for both existing and new copyright works, taking it from 50 to 70 years. Professor Lawrence Lessig and Eric Eldred challenged the constitutionality of the Act in the case of *Eldred v Ashcroft* on the ground that the continued extension of copyright terms as done by the Act contravenes the copyright clause and the right to freedom of expression in the US constitution. The US supreme court affirmed the constitutionality of the act and dismissed the argument of Lawrence and Eldred.

Professor Lawrence, with a strong desire to assist Americans and the world at large to have access to knowledge and information with little or no restriction, with the support of few like minds, launched the Creative Commons in order to pursue this goal.

Creative commons (cc) is a global non-profit organization whose aim is to enable the sharing and reuse of creativity and knowledge through the provision of free legal tools. It is an American founded organization with international networks which

develop educational access and expanding the range of creative works available for others to build upon legally and to share.

Creative commons (cc) was founded in January 15th, 2001 by Prof Lawrence Lessig, James Boyle and Hal Abelson with the general support of the Centre for Public Domain, Fellows and Students at the Berkman Centre for Internet and Society at Harvard Law School, and Stanford Law School Centre for Internet and Society. It has its headquarters in Mountain view, California, United States with its members (Commons) spread across the world. It has National Chapters in over 43 countries of the world, each chapter coordinating the works of individual members, donors of creative works and organization that support the Creative Commons Global Network.

The mission of Creative commons is to help the world overcome legal obstacle to the sharing of knowledge and creativity, and to ensure open access to creative works for research, use, reuse and remix. Creative commons aims at bridging the gulf in knowledge and information inequality. It therefore provide legal tools for authors to offer their copyrighted works for use, reuse and remix under generous and standardise terms.

Creative Commons achieve its mission by –

- i. Providing CC Licences and public domain tools that give every person and organization in the world a free, simple and standardised way to grant copyright permission for creative and academic works.
- ii. Work closely with major institutions and governments to create, adopt and implement open licences and cc Licensed contents.
- iii. Support the CC Global Network which is a community initiative working to create the volume, breadth and quality of openly available knowledge worldwide.
- iv. Offers CC certificate, an in-depth course for people interested in becoming experts in creating and engaging with openly licensed works.

Creative commons has over 1.6 billion works in its network and under its licenses and still counting. These CC licensed creative works ranges from literary works, to

videos, photos, audio, open education, scientific research and more. Online platforms in which CC licensed work can be found includes but not limited to Wiki, Flickr, Sound cloud and YouTube.

Creative commons (CC) and its legal tool is a mechanism or instrument available for balancing the copyright of authors of creative works and the need to have open and liberal access to use, reuse, distribute and modify creative works with little or no liability for copyright infringement.

3.0 CREATIVE COMMONS IN NIGERIA

Creative commons has extended its network to Nigeria by establishing an affiliate team called creative commons Nigeria. Its vision is to encourage creativity through information and knowledge-sharing, and to encourage creative common licensing in Nigeria. Access to knowledge and knowledge sharing are concepts that have great potentials to serve the needs of the huge educational sector in Nigeria. The same goes for the rapidly growing creative industry and its teaming creative individuals in need of base resources to further ignite their creative instinct.

In effort to achieve its goals, creative commons Nigeria is embarking on the following project inter alia –

1. Organizing conferences targeting deans and vice chancellors of tertiary institutions in Nigeria, in collaboration with Office for Technology acquisition and promotion (NOTAP)
2. Attending and presenting papers at public events in order to create awareness about CC and open access policies.
3. Collaborating with relevant institutions to create awareness and conduct workshop/trainings on creative commons and its policies.
4. Designing and executing research project on open education resources and open education practice in public schools in Nigeria.
5. Also working on translating cc licence deeds to raise awareness amongst diverse committee of stakeholders.

Creative commons licensing model could serve as a strategic policy initiative for the Nigerian government to address some of the challenges of access to educational resources for both teachers and students. The success of cc in driving these goals in Nigeria will depend on creating awareness about the nature and benefit of cc licensing and securing government supports and endorsement.

Creative commons Nigeria is organized into three sections of volunteers –

1. CC Nigeria –Legal Lead: this is a team of legal expert who understand licensing issue. This team gives legal advice to the Community (cc Nigeria).
2. CC Nigeria – Public Lead: this is meant to be a public institution that has influence in government’s legal policy making.
3. CC Nigeria – Technical lead, this team is to handle technical issues. It has the onus to bridge the technological divide to the legal practitioners.

A strong CC presence in Nigeria will strengthen the synergy geared towards entrenching CC licenses and its objectives in Nigeria. The mission of CC Nigeria is to build a community of creative minds and grow strong networks that will encourage knowledge sharing through training, outreach, workshops and related avenues. In order to attain its goals, CC Nigeria needs strong collaborations and supports from CC Global and other CC communities around the world especially CC Communities in Africa such as CC South Africa, CC Kenya and CC Uganda.

4.0 CREATIVE COMMONS (CC) LICENSE

These are licenses issued by creative commons (CC) to creators of creative works who donate their works to it. It is one of the several copyright licenses that enable free distribution, use and reuse of an otherwise copyrighted works without infringing on the copyright of such works. CC License is used by a creator or copyright holder who wants to give other people the right to share, use, reuse and build upon the work he has created. CC License shields those who used the works licensed under it from being held liable for infringement provided the terms of the CC license are complied with. It is based on the terms contained in the CC License that the donor i.e., the creator allows his work to be used and distributed.

CC licences and tools forge a balance inside the traditional “all right reserved” setting that copyright law creates. This licence is a tool that gives everyone, from individual creators to large companies and institutions a simple, standardized way to grant copyright permissions to their creative works

CC licences are of several types, each differing in the combination of terms and conditions for distribution and use. There have been about four versions of cc license numbered 1.0 to 4.0 with the 4.0 as the current version. Some of creative commons licences are CC by, CC BY-SA and CC licences.

The whole philosophy behind Creative Commons and its license tools is to enable creators to retain copyright while allowing others to copy, distribute, and make use of their works. It has been stated that the most well-known open license model for open educational research (OER) is the CC licences.

CC Licences are a standardized suite of six licences that may be applied to any work protected by copyright and associated rights (such as database rights). They are free, easy-to use legal tools designed to facilitate making copyrighted materials available to the public so that they can be legally shared, remixed and reused

The terms for which a creator of creative work can allow his work to be used under cc license varies. They include; Non-commercial use, Non derivative, Educational, Attribution, Share-Alike etc. It could be a combination of any of the above listed terms and conditions. The term may require the user to make his new work derived from the cc licensed work available for use under the same terms. This is called “Share-Alike”. Share-Alike is a tool which CC believes that if properly utilized will lead to the growth and expansion of creative works over the times.

CC Licences are uniquely made in three-layer designs. The first comes in form of legal code in which lawyers understand. The second layer comes in form of a deed called common deed or human readable for non-lawyers to understand, the last layer design recognises that software plays an enormous role in the creation, copying, discovery and distribution of works and because of this fact, a “machine readable” version of the license is created. The “machine readable” version of CC licence is a summary of the key freedoms and obligations written into a format that software

systems, search engines and other kinds of technology can understand. The three layer designs in summary are – a. Legal Code; b. Common Deed/ User Readable; and c. Machine Readable.

The six existing CC licences are –

- a. Attribution – CC BY
- b. Attribution – CC BY – SA (Share-Alike)
- c. Attribution – CC BY – ND (Non Derivative)
- d. Attribution – CC BY – NC (Non Commercial)
- e. Attribution – CC BY – NC – SA
- f. Attribution – CC BY – NC – ND

While the first type of license above is the least restrictive as it allows for use, reuse, share and remix with little or no restriction, the last mentioned type of licence is the most restrictive.

5.1 CREATIVE COMMONS (CC) LICENCE AND COPYRIGHT

Creative Commons (CC) licences work in legal systems around the world. These licences are framed in line with and within national copyright laws. They are supplementary to traditional copyright and do not replace it, the two coexist side by side. CC licences are meant to define clearly which set of copy rights are free for users and which ones are restricted. CC licences are useful only because of the existence of copyrights and its excessive protection in creative work. An author of a creative work uses cc licence instrument to waive certain aspects of his copyrights to enable the use, reuse, share and remix of his work within the terms of the licence.

Rather than the traditional total or absolute copyright over creative works, usually put as “all rights reserved”, CC licence reduces some rights of the creator by specifying the terms and condition therein. CC licence is a copyright licence that is given by the owner of a creative work (Licensor) to the user (licensee) to use a work in accordance with the terms and condition stated therein. CC licence can be said to be a voluntary tool for the reduction of copyrights of authors of creative works for

the purpose of open knowledge, knowledge and information circulation; and the enhancement of creativity, innovation and development.

It is pertinent to state here that, a creative work already in the public domain either due to exhaustion, lapse of copyright, or which does not meet criteria for copyright protection is not worthy of CC licence. This is because the goal of creative commons is to make as much as possible copyrighted works available and accessible to the public with little or no restriction. Therefore, if a work is in the public domain, CC licence is absolutely unnecessary. It therefore suffices to say that CC licence lives because there is copyright.

The issue of CC Licence and copyright infringement has been pronounced upon by the courts in several cases across several jurisdictions. In the US case of *Great Minds v Office Depot, Inc.*, Great Minds is a non-profit organization that publishes educational materials, including a copyrighted maths curriculum available under a CC license allowing non-commercial use only. Office Depot made copies of the maths curriculum on behalf of schools and school districts. The parties initially entered into a licensing agreement, but Office Depot terminated the agreement after the *Great Minds v FedEx Office* district court decision, which held that FedEx could make copies of the materials at the request of school districts exercising their rights under the CC license. Great Minds then filed A suit for copyright infringement and breach of contract in Federal Court in California, US.

The district court in the Central district of California dismissed the copyright infringement claim, holding that the CC license permitted the school districts to use contractors to exercise their rights under the license. Great Minds appealed to the Ninth Circuit Court of Appeals, which affirmed the lower court decision. Creative Commons intervened as amicus curiae, arguing that CC licenses are designed to allow licensees to use contractors to exercise their rights under the license.

In *Great Minds v FedEx Office & Print Services, Inc.*, FedEx Office made copies of the maths curriculum on behalf of schools and school districts. Great Minds filed suit for copyright infringement in federal court in New York. FedEx Office filed a motion to dismiss, arguing that Great Minds did not state a valid copyright infringement claim because FedEx Office was acting on behalf of a bona fide licensee under the

relevant CC license. Great Minds asserted that FedEx Office itself was a licensee under the CC license and thereby violated the non commercial restriction by charging for reproduction of the material. The district court granted the motion to dismiss, holding that the school districts were permitted to use third parties like the defendant to exercise their rights under the CC license. The Second Circuit Court of Appeal affirmed the lower court decision.

In the German case of Gerlachs v DVU , the plaintiff took a picture of the German politician Thilo Sarrazin at a public event and published it online under a Creative Commons ShareAlike license. Later the DVU, a German political party, used the picture on their website without the plaintiff's name, the license notice, or a link to the original work. The photographer sent a takedown notice to the political party, which was ignored. Subsequently, the photographer sought an injunction preventing the DVU from continuing use of the photograph. The court ruled that the DVU's use was not in compliance with the CC license and granted the injunction as prayed.

In No. 71036 v Newspaper, a newspaper used several CC-licensed photos in an issue of the newspaper without proper attribution. The photographer contacted the newspaper about the omission, and the newspaper offered the photographer 400 Sheqels, which was the price they said they would have paid a photographer to take a similar photo. The photographer did not accept the offer and brought suit for copyright infringement. Though not decided by an official Israeli court but by a private Rabbinical Tribunal, the Tribunal analyzed the case under both the Torah and the Israel Copyright Act and held that there is a religious or moral obligation to comply with the attribution terms of the CC licenses. It found the Newspaper's settlement offer to be below the value of the benefit the Newspaper had received from using the photo and noted that the Israel copyright Act provides for damages up to 100,000 Sheqel. The Tribunal found for the photographer and awarded the sum of 3,500 Sheqel.

In the Dutch case of Curry v Audax, Adam Curry, a former MTV VJ and one of the pioneers of podcasting, published photos onto his Flickr account under a BY-NC-SA 2.0 license. A dutch tabloid reprinted four of the photos in a story about the curry family. Curry sued the tabloid for violating his privacy rights and for copyright

infringement. The court held that the tabloid had violated the CC license on the images by failing to attach a notice about the license and for using the images in a commercial magazine. However, the court did not award damages to the plaintiff because they could not prove harm. The court held that defendant could not use any of the photos from Flickr in the future unless they comply with the terms of the CC license or with permission from the plaintiff.

In another case of *Lichodmapwa v L'asbl Festival de Theatre de Spa*, the Belgian band Lichodmapwa released the song “Abatchouck” under CC BY-NC-ND 2.5 Belgium license. Several years later, one of the band members heard a portion of the song in an advertisement for a theatre festival run by a non-profit organization. Lichodmapwa contacted the organization to see if they could negotiate a deal. The negotiations failed, and Lichodmapwa sued the organization for copyright infringement.

The court recognized the validity of the Creative Commons license applied to the music, and held that the plaintiff’s decision not to join the collecting society (SABAM) and instead to release their music more openly should not prevent them from enforcing their copyright. The court held that the good faith of the defendant was not an excuse for violating the license. As a festival organizer regularly involved in licensing, the court said the defendant should have known to look for and follow the terms of the license. The court noted that the website from which the theatre downloaded the music, ‘<http://www.dogmazic.net>’ clearly mentions the CC license. The court awarded the plaintiff 1,500 Euros per license condition violated, 4,500 Euros in total.

It is worthy to state here that CC Licence has not been seen or taken as a permanent solution to the excessive protection regime offered by copyright law.

6.0 RECOMMEDATION

In view of the challenges posed by the rigid copyright regime to access to knowledge, information, research, educational materials, and the mechanism provided by Creative Commons, we offer useful recommendations herein.

Governments across the world should take into account the dire need for open access to knowledge and information; and access to educational and learning materials while reviewing copyright and other intellectual property laws.

Parliaments across the world should carry out amendments to copyright enactments aimed at demystifying the strong and rigid copyright protection.

Copyright owners should fully embrace and utilise the creative common Licence window and allow people to have access to their works with little or no restrictions.

The governments need to make robust policies towards creative commons and open Education Resource with the aim of addressing the challenges of access to educational and research materials.

Creative commons in the various countries of the world should formulate policies and programmes for advocacy awareness and vigorously implement same.

Governments, authors and consumers of creative works need to know about the invaluable mechanism made available by creative commons via it creative common licences so as to take full advantage of same.

7.0 CONCLUSION

Copyright protection ab initio was conferred on authors of creative works as incentive for creativity. However, it turned out to be a hindrance to creativity and access to information and knowledge. This is because copyright protection over the time became expanded and elongated hence its rigid regime with huge legal restrictions on the use of copyright materials. creative commons and creative commons licence emerged as a direct response to the shortcomings of copyright laws and licensing practices. creative commons licences offer authors and users of copyright works the opportunity to navigate / sail through the copyright rigid restrictions. Since the formation and launched of creative commons and its licence much has changed about the use, reuse and share of copyrighted creative works. There has been a reasonable unlocking of access to knowledge and information. As authors are encouraged to embrace creative common licence mechanism, parliaments are called to review copyright statutes with a view to demystifying its rigid protection.

Abstract

1. Zohar Efroni, *Access-Right* (New York, Oxford University Press, 2011)120.
2. Garnet K, Davies G and Harbottle G., *Copinger & Skone James on Copyright* (15th Ed. London, Sweet & Maxwell, 2005)1.
3. Craige Joyce et al, *Copyright Law* (New York, LEXIS Publishing, 1998, 15.
4. Gretche McCord Hoffman, *Copyright in Cyberspace: Questions and answers for librarians* (New York, Neal-Schuman Publishers, Inc, 2001), 5.
5. Craige, (n 5).
6. Statute of Anne, Copyright Act, 1710, section 11.
7. *Eldred v Ashcroft* (2003) 537, U.S. 186 (SC).
8. Sections 3 and 4 of US Copyright Act 1790.
9. Copyright Act, Cap C 28, LFN, 2004, First schedule.
10. Copyright Act, Cap C 28, LFN, 2004, section 1.
11. Ibid, section 6.
12. Julien Cabay and Maxime Lambrecht, 'Remix Prohibited – How Rigid EU Copyright Laws Inhibit Creativity'(2015) (10) (5), *Journal of intellectual property law and practice*, 359-377
13. Copyright Act, Cap C28, LFN 2004.
14. [2002] Ch. 149 at 163 (CA).
15. Justice Story, *Emerson v Davies* (1845) 8 F. Cas. 615, 619
16. Pamela Samuelson, 'Justification for Copyright Limitations & Exceptions' PDF, available at <www.law.berkeley.edu> accessed 10 November 2021.
17. Which include; Fair dealing/use, permitted purposes, Acknowledgement, Innocent Infringement etc.

18. In Nigerian for instance, by the provisions of paragraph 1 of the First Schedule to the Copyright Act, Cap C28, LFN, 2004, copyright in Literary, Musical and Artistic works is for the duration of the life time of the author and 70 years after the death of the author.
19. For example, the protection for the life time of an author and seventy years after the demise of the author for copyright in literary, artistic and musical work is clearly excessive and overly protective.
20. Stanford Law Professor at the time.
21. An internet publisher who had a career in making freely available creative works as they passed into the public domain.
22. *Eldred v Ashcroft* (2003) 537, U.S. 186 (SC).
23. Denise R. Nicolson, 'How Creative Commons Works and why it enable access to knowledge' <<https://theconversation.com>> accessed 8 May 2021.
24. <<https://creativecommons.org> > accessed 8 May 2021.
25. Creative Commons Nigeria, <<https://creativecommons.org/nigeria>> accessed 14 May 2021.
26. Creative Commons, 'Creative Commons Licences' <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses>> accessed 8 May 2021.
27. Maximiliano Marzetti, 'Open Educational Resources for emergency remote teaching – Anew paradigm' <<https://theconversation.com>> accessed 8 May 2021.
28. Fitzgerald A. and Hooper N., 'Budget papers are free to share, thanks to Creative Commons' <<https://theconversation.com>> accessed 8 May 2021.
29. AJE Scholar, 'Creative Common licenses: An Introduction for Researchers' <<https://www.aje.com>> accessed 8 May 2021; Kayode Yussuf, 'Creative Commons Nigeria: the journey so far and the journey ahead' <<https://www.slideshare.net>> accessed 14 May 2021.

30. *Minds v Office Depot, Inc* (2019) No. 18-55331 US (9th Cir.) (CA)
31. *Great Minds v FedEx Office & Print Services, Inc*, No. 17-808 (2d Cir. 2018)
<<https://law.justia.com/cases/federal/appellate-courts/ca2/17-808/17-808-2018-03-21.html>> accessed 7 May 2021.
32. Ibid.
33. *Gerlachs v DVU*, (2010) (unreported), cited in ‘Creative Commons, Attribution, Sharealike License Enforced in Germany’
<<https://creativecommons.org/2011/09/15/>> accessed 7 May 2021.
34. *No. 71036* (2011) (unreported), <<https://legaldb.creativecommons.org/cases/9/>>
accessed 11 November 2021.
35. *Curry* (2006) (unreported), <<https://legaldb.creativecommons.org/cases/3/>>
accessed 11 November 2021.
36. *Lichodmapwa* 08-1684-A (2010),
<<https://legaldb.creativecommons.org/cases/7/>> accessed 11 November 2021.